

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: O'BLENESS****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024 have formulated a hierarchical scheme that is not unlike Maslow's hierarchy of human needs. This hierarchical structure is supported by which of the following statements?

- This hierarchical structure requires that there be a linear approach to writing an academic essay.
- This hierarchical structure follows a systematic approach to writing an academic essay, including avoiding procrastination, answering key questions, and designing an initial plan.¹**
- This hierarchical structure lacks support for incorporating provisional answers to proposed hypotheses.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024). 7.

- This hierarchical structure relies on rhetorical published works as a means of producing nonfictional writing.
2. Identifying the type and source of data is essential to understanding how it fits into and supports dissertation research. Sources may have overlapping themes, but each has a specific role in validating background research. Which of the following statements is true?
- Secondary resources contain literature ascribed to specific fields of study and are historically based. This body of knowledge is subsequent literature or research based on extant resources.
- Much of the body of knowledge on specific subjects can be cited or referenced through an internet search engine and is reliable, having been vetted by peer review.
- Primary resources contain original research and raw data in vetted journals and sanctioned databases. Research is conducted based on primary resources.**²
- Comparative databases, such as PubMed or the Cochran Comparative Database, are only relevant to researchers and librarians who need historical background information.
3. The goal of any researcher is original inquiry addressing gaps in the literature or additional insights into novel ways of utilizing existing research. Which of the following statements best describes what a line of questioning needs to accomplish?

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

- By asking 'why' gathering data supporting their own need to answer the question of interest.
 - By validating the significance of the research topic beyond personal interest by answering, 'So what?' is the relevance of the problem question to a larger academic or professional group.³**
 - Satisfying the researcher's curiosity by crafting questions relevant to the researcher and their interest.
 - Attracting peer readership by appealing to disciplines outside of the researcher's field of expertise.
4. Quantitative research promotes objectivity, contending that limiting and containing the potential for bias to affect research results is possible. The researcher must be cognizant of intentional and unintentional sources of bias. Which statement best represents an understanding of sources for bias?
- The researcher believes the findings have a discordant relationship to the variables or the efficacy of the intervention.
 - The researcher overtly disregard alternative views, believing that choosing literature supporting the proposed research strengthens their argument.

³ Ibid., 21.

- The researcher acknowledges that the experiential use of a specific strategy and its perceived effectiveness or ineffectiveness may result in intervention bias.⁴**
- The researcher's point of view is blinded to the operational definition of terms.
5. Researchers consider their questions in the context of being practical or conceptual in the physical environment, practical problems address real-time conditions with an associated cost-benefit relationship, presupposing an outcome. Knowledge gained is the essence of a conceptual problem. Which statement is true?
- Researchers chose a topic based on familiarity and practical application, generating provocative questions that are easily answered.
- Asking questions that are in disagreement with a peer-reviewed source may make the novice researcher appear naïve.
- Researchers often reject a question based on assuming the question would differ from conventional wisdom without exploring the possibility of offering a better answer or perspective.⁵**
- Considering how the research question is formed, an unfocused topic emerges from sifting through sources and data gathering.

⁴ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 16.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 28.

6. As an abstract structure, developing a schema for organizing and remembering information and sequencing complex tasks is an initial task for doctoral students.

Which statement best describes how developing a schema aids the researcher?

- The development of a schema for each concept of the dissertation is broadly categorized into various sections, such as methodology or philosophical underpinnings.
- A procedural schema aids the learner in understanding the sequential steps in completing a complex task. Using a procedural schema develops new knowledge as tasks are completed, which becomes the requisite knowledge for subsequent tasks.⁶**
- A well-developed procedural schema will drive the dissertation research, validating the researcher's proposition even if a research question is flawed.
- In the sequencing of the dissertation sections, providing possible answers to the research question is independent of the research design.

7. Turabian 2018 stresses that creating an argument is central to what research is. When constructing an effective argument, the researcher considers key concepts. Of the following statements which best defines an argument?

- An understanding that an argument is contextual and within the research community is, by design, meant to sequester arguments contrary to the proposed solution to the problem statement.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 16.

- As the researcher develops an argument for their case there may be cause to realign the research question and hypothesis as a draft proposal is prepared.**⁷
 - The researcher constructs an imaginary conversation with potential readers of the dissertation research, developing reasoned evidence that leads the reader to a specific conclusion.
 - The dissertation thesis is a claim demanding supporting evidence that cannot be argued.
8. Gathering background information to corroborate the researcher's thesis requires the ethical treatment of others' research. Which statement reflects best practice to avoid plagiarism?
- It remains the reader's duty to ascertain the veracity of the citations presented by the dissertation researcher.
 - In creating a valid argument, it is necessary to guard against plagiarism through proper citation of work that is not the researcher's original thoughts, propositions, or conclusions.**⁸
 - In dissertation research, it is contrary to establishing the fidelity of the researcher's proposition to present citations that are not supportive of the conclusions made by the researcher.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 56.

⁸ Ibid., 140.

- Utilizing citations that are not quoted or paraphrased should be avoided, as such may lead the reader to extraneous conclusions not aligned with the stated proposition.
9. The interpretation of the findings may be skewed by subjective bias from the researcher. This bias can be mitigated by transparently examining the limitations and constraints anticipated and encountered by the researcher. Which statement best addresses transparency in the findings?
- The boundaries of the dissertation are restrictions clarified by the limiting of what will be examined.
- The implications for transparency in the interpretation of findings are that future studies would be questionable using the dissertation research methodology.
- Delimitations are not useful in shaping the readers' expectations of how the current study results have implications for generalizability to other populations.
- Expressed threats to internal and external validity are of concern to the researcher and the intended audience, composing one of the constraints on interpreting the findings.⁹**
10. Considering research methodology, the dissertation researcher must also evaluate the instrument they chose to gather data. Representative of the instrument selected is the comparative ability of the instrument to render normative group comparisons to a larger population. Which statement is true?

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

- Standardization is concerned with the extent to which the norm groups for an instrument or test are appropriate for the populations for which the instrument or test was designed.¹⁰**
- Sampling error is evidenced by the adequate size and randomness of normative groups to mirror representative populations.
- The dissertation researcher documents evidence that the instrument or test used to gather data was discordant in accounting for inherent biases related to the general population.
- Controlling for population characteristics is independent of constructing a control group representative of the researcher's desired population characteristics.

¹⁰ Ibid.

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